

Predicting procrastination, academic failure and anxiety based on parenting styles

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Abstract

The current research was conducted with the aim of predicting work procrastination, academic failure and anxiety based on parents' parenting styles on the students of Arak city. This study was descriptive-correlation type. It was in the academic year of 1399-1400. 300 people were selected as a research sample by random cluster sampling. In order to collect information, the standard procrastination questionnaires of Solomon Wrathblum (1984), the Phillips School Anxiety Questionnaire (1978), and the Diana Baumrind Parenting Styles Questionnaire (1972) were used, as well as the scores obtained by students at the end of each academic semester. The data were analyzed by Pearson's correlation test and multiple linear regression analysis. The findings showed that there is a significant relationship between work procrastination, academic failure and anxiety with the components of parents' parenting style. Also, the results of the regression analysis showed that parents' parenting styles significantly predict procrastination, academic failure and anxiety ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the need to pay attention to the parenting styles of parents should be given more attention. [1].

Keywords: Parenting styles, Procrastination, Academic failure, Anxiety, Students.

1. INTRODUCTION

Family is the main unit of human experience and the most important social environment that affects people's growth. A person is influenced not only physically and biologically, but also in terms of personality, by his early experiences in the family environment. Family processes and actions, such as the quality of parent-child communication, have a great impact on the development of the sense of self-worth and social adequacy in childhood. Psychologists have realized that parenting methods have a great impact on many psychological aspects such as social adaptation, self-esteem, self-confidence and success in work and behavioral problems in adolescence. (Balbi and Freud, 1964, quoted from Broumandnasb, 1373). Darling and Steinberg (1993; cited by Glasgow, Dornbuch, Trevor et al., 1997) have defined parenting practices as follows: Parenting practices are a set of tendencies, actions and non-verbal manifestations that characterize the nature of child-parent interaction. It specifies in all different situations and it has been proposed in three domains: authoritarian, authoritarian and permissive. One of the effective factors in the level of students' performance is anxiety. Discomfort caused by moderate anxiety forces a person to discover different ways to avoid anxiety, which is a learning process [2]. Increasing anxiety to a certain extent is a stimulus for learning, but the increase of anxiety to a significant extent causes lack of learning and has the opposite result. Parents through their parenting styles have very important and significant effects on the academic progress of their children at different levels of education. Children and teenagers need trust, support, and close relationships with their families, especially their parents, to succeed

in higher education and in their lives. Academic failure is also said to reduce the student's academic performance from a satisfactory level to an unfavorable level. Paying attention to the above points shows that the comparison and measurement of the student's previous and current academic performance is the best indicator of academic failure. Another factor that should be considered in this context is academic procrastination. Procrastination is usually defined as an irrational tendency to delay responsibilities, homework decisions that must be completed (Felt, Blankstein, Hewitt, and Kaldin, 1992). Academic procrastination is one of the important factors of students' failure or lack of success in learning and academic progress, which sometimes has negative and irreparable consequences for students (Nasri, Damavandi and Ashuri, 2013). Observing such ups and downs in students' academic performance calls us to investigate its causes. Because the education system is one of the most expensive organizations and institutions in the country [2]. And also because of its vital value in providing and training skilled and expert human resources of the society and in general the cultural and economic upliftment of the country, investigating the causes of academic failure, procrastination and anxiety of students and the methods to deal with it, can be avoided. prevent the material and spiritual capitals of people and officials and lead to the maximum efficiency of the people of the society. For this reason, we seek to predict the amount of procrastination, academic failure and anxiety of students through parenting styles.[3].

2. Statement of the research problem

Healthy families are the basis of a healthy society. Every person is born in a family, grows up and evolves. It is a healthy family that raises a healthy person.[4] The family is the first social unit in which children and adolescents experience their cognitive, social, emotional and psychological growth, so parents' parenting methods have a great impact on how children and adolescents grow and develop their personality. From the moment of birth to adulthood, children in the family have well absorbed the characteristics and behaviors of their family environment and their actions and behavior are a reflection of all their perceptions of the environment in which they grew up. Parenting practices as a set or system of behaviors that describe parent-child interactions during a wide range of situations and have been hypothesized to produce an affective interactional component. The factor of socialization in the life of every person is his childhood experiences in the family environment. The atmosphere of the family is full of affection, sacrifice and forgiveness, intimacy and warmth, but at the same time it is sometimes accompanied by jealousy, enmity, malice, hatred and anger.[5] Darling and Steinberg consider parenting styles as one of the characteristics of parents, which by adjusting the specific actions that parents do and changing the experience of children in the process of socialization, they define the efforts of parents as a set of attitudes of parents towards children that are expressed in relation to children. And they create an emotional atmosphere. in which parents' behaviors are expressed. These behaviors include specific behaviors and targeted behaviors that are applied by each of the parents to perform their parental duties, as well as non-targeted behaviors of parents including gestures, changes in voice tone, or improvisational expression of emotions. Diana Baumrind has presented the most famous family parenting styles.[5] He considers parenting styles to include three styles: authoritarian (democracy, free-spirited), autocratic (dictatorship, dominance) and permissive (indifference, chaos). Parenting style is about the child, the way to communicate with the child, the method of keeping the child and the emotional aspect that governs the behavioral space of the parents. What is certain and makes the research about the parenting styles of parents necessary is that in the family system, if the relations of each member with the other are disturbed, in this case, the whole family system will have problems, which are sometimes difficult to compensate and some Sometimes it is impossible.[6] Meanwhile, naturally, the weakest and smallest members of the family, who are children, will be more affected. In the meantime, parents should establish a proper education system in the family system to prevent such problems. According to the conducted research such as Monica (2014) and Afzali (2012), among the many factors influencing students' education, family and parents' communication patterns can play a significant role in maintaining mental, social, physical health and academic progress. In other words, the first social base in all stages of life, especially in the teenage years, which plays an important role in regulating the thoughts, feelings and behavior of teenagers, is the family relationship (Yousfi and Fehandari, 2010).[7] According to the explanations and researches, it seems that the parenting styles of the family have a significant effect on the formation of the children's personality and how they deal with challenging situations.[7] The family can nurture people in such a way that they can prepare themselves to face difficult situations, this preparation strengthens adaptive and effective coping

strategies. As a result, they use problem solving methods instead of avoiding solving tasks and responsibilities. Also, the family can provide grounds for cultivating creative thinking by providing a friendly and warm atmosphere where children have the opportunity to participate in decisions and express opinions. That makes teenagers not accept the information they get in the school environment and in society in general and prevent them from suffering from various social harms. The family is also the basis for the formation of people's personality and characteristics such as order, positive perfectionism, lack of fear of failure, high self-esteem and conscientiousness, which have been proven in various researches on the relationship between these variables and procrastination. [8]

The success or failure of students in education is one of the most important concerns of any educational system. Because their academic success and progress shows the success of the educational system in terms of targeting and attention to the individual needs of students; Therefore, the educational system of a society can be considered successful when its students have the highest level of academic progress in all levels of education. Therefore, educational experts and experts believe that every educational system should be able to identify the factors affecting academic progress and adjust and guide them in a way that leads to the growth and learning of students. (Alexander and Anogbazi, 2014). [9]

One of the complex behaviors is procrastination or postponing things to the future. A habit that exists in many people. As far as the researchers believe that this feature is one of the innate human tendencies. Procrastination is an act that, at first glance, aims to make life pleasant. But in most cases, it has no other consequences except stress, confusion and successive failures. And it is worth mentioning that procrastination is not always a problem. But in most cases, it can bring adverse and irreparable consequences by hindering progress and not reaching the goals. (Shokri and Golestani Bakht, 1392).[9] Procrastination is not a new phenomenon. William James recognized the psychological consequences of procrastination 120 years ago. Vastil (2007). He discovered the sources of procrastination dating back to 800 BC (Clasen, Krucek and Rajani, 2008). Procrastination leads to unproductive work. Procrastination is a time thief and makes a person feel guilty and changes the way others look at him. Today, it has become a fact that being productive, being active and completing assignments are very valuable skills. While postponing work and procrastination is a direct violation of accepted norms of doing things (Hashmian and Latifian, 1392).[10] Many definitions have been given of procrastination; Stevenson (2013) considers procrastination as postponing or postponing to another time. Also, the concept of procrastination has been proposed in scientific studies in a more comprehensive way than the definition given in the dictionary. Procrastination behavior is defined as postponing tasks to a later time and for several reasons (Yaziki and Balat 2015).[11]

On the other hand, procrastination sometimes causes irreparable harm to students and because of its negative results, it has been one of the issues of interest to experts in recent years (Hosseini Nasab and Lotfollahi, 1392). Also, students procrastinate and postpone preparation for the exam until the final night, and as a result, they experience severe anxiety during the exam.[12] They also report low self-esteem due to high experience of anxiety and depression. (Lai and Silverman, 1996; Fathi, Fathi Azar, Badri and Mirnasab

2014), in addition, psychologists believe that academic procrastination has a direct effect on students' academic progress (Paula Rascapa, 2015; Kim and Su, 2015).[13]

Education is the best factor in the transfer of material and spiritual capital and a means for the sustainability of the development and evolution of the social system, and if these changes do not take place in a society, we must seek to know the causes to find a solution to realize it. In this context, academic failure is known as one of the educational plagues and one of the existing problems of the education system of any country (Dehesh, 2013).[14]

Academic dropout has been more and more noticed by education specialists in the last few decades. Findings have shown that academic dropout is also affected by knowledge structures and information processing processes. Due to the importance of the phenomenon of educational attrition and the variables affecting it, and also because the children of each family are considered as the capital of a country, educational attrition is of special importance in them. Considering that children grow and are educated in the family environment. Parents' educational model plays an important role in their children's academic progress or failure. Therefore, the need to investigate the relationship between parenting styles and students' academic performance can be justified. Academic failure can be defined as follows; A student who fails in the process of education at a level and level of education. A grade repeater is a child or adolescent who repeats a grade. A decline in academic quality means that a student's academic status is not at the desired or usual level. Failure to achieve educational goals and objectives, in other words, any factor that reduces the efficiency of school, family, or society in terms of achieving educational goals, is a kind of waste. Therefore, any type of failure in any aspect of education work may be the source of loss.[15]

Another factor affecting student performance is anxiety. Anxiety plays an important role in learning. Anxiety activates human intelligence and is a solid solution to focus and achieve satisfactory results and rewards. The discomfort of moderate anxiety forces us to discover different ways of avoiding anxiety, and this in itself is a learning process. However, there is a complex relationship between anxiety and learning. Increasing anxiety to a certain extent is a stimulus to increase learning. But after this certain level, the increase in anxiety causes a decrease in learning, and if the level of anxiety increases again, it will cause the lack of motivation for learning and will lead to more risk in errors and mistakes. This means that there is an optimal level of anxiety for optimal learning.[15]

After this level of increase, anxiety has the opposite effect and is counterproductive. Anxiety is considered as a part of every human life in every society as a suitable and adaptive response. Lack of anxiety or morbid anxiety may expose us to many problems and dangers. Balanced and constructive anxiety forces us to do our jobs in a timely and appropriate manner, thus making our lives more durable and productive. we build. It rarely happens that anxiety crises are not observed during the adolescent process. Sometimes this anxiety appears suddenly and sometimes gradually. Sometimes it is pervasive and sometimes it ends in a few hours. Therefore, anxiety is a part of the life of children and teenagers, it forms one of the components of their personality structure, and it is from this angle that some of the anxieties of childhood and adolescence can be considered as the norm and their positive influence in the transformation process can be accepted. Because it provides an

opportunity for people to develop their coping mechanisms in the direction of dealing with stressful and anxiety-provoking sources. On the contrary, there is also morbid anxiety, which is considered as a source of failure and irreconcilability, and includes a wide range of unjustified cognitive and physical disorders and panic, and deprives a person of a major part of his possibilities. (Prosecutor, 1376). In this research, according to the importance of the issue and the cognitive and personality characteristics of the sixth-grade students, which is comparable to the teenage age, and the variables of procrastination, academic failure and anxiety as predictor variables and parenting styles as criterion variables will be discussed.[16]

According to the results of various researches, it seems that there is a relationship between family parenting styles, academic procrastination, academic failure, and anxiety. Therefore, this research aims to determine whether there is a structural relationship between parenting styles and the three variables of procrastination and check the academic drop and anxiety of students. Given that the procrastination and anxiety of students along with their academic failure are influential factors in a person's personal and social life, and these factors may cause students to drop out of school and become disconnected from the education process.[16] Also, dropping out of education has long-term costs and consequences for both them and society. The researcher is trying to answer this question: Can parenting styles of parents predict academic failure, anxiety and procrastination of students? [16]

3. The importance and necessity of doing this research

Family, as the first social center, has various factors, one of the factors influencing children's growth, especially their psychological growth, is how the parenting methods are used in the family framework. The educational method of parents is effective in the development of personality as well as their adaptation to different social situations. Favorable relationships between parents and children have a great impact on children's mental health. Parents and children are among the important issues that have attracted the attention of experts and education experts for years. In Islamic texts, parenting is a complex activity that includes behaviors, training, interactions and methods that affect growth separately and in interaction with each other. Spiritually, emotionally, it affects the individual and social dimensions. From the point of view of Islam, the responsibility of raising a child during childhood rests with the parents. As far as it is considered one of the children's rights (Parcham et al., 2011).[17]

From the moment of birth to adulthood in the family, children absorb the traits, behaviors and characteristics of the family environment and their actions and behavior are a reflection of all their perceptions of the environment in which they grew up., social and emotional of children. Since adolescence is one of the most critical stages of life, failure to respond to needs leaves a very destructive effect on them. Also, since the children of each family are considered as the capital of a country, the phenomenon of academic failure, procrastination and anxiety of students is of special importance. Due to the fact that children grow and are educated in the family environment. The educational model of parents plays an important role in the growth and academic progress of their children. Therefore, investigating the relationship between parenting styles and procrastination, anxiety, and academic failure seems necessary.[18]

The construction of the family and the place that the child occupies in the family plays an important role in the development of his personality. Some studies have concluded that there is an important relationship between the level of family functioning and the variables of aggression, deprivation, fear, anxiety and hyperactivity in children. Family functioning is a quality that is affected by many psychological-personality, socio-economic and cultural factors. [18] System theorists consider the family as a system where members are influenced by each other. So that the functioning of the family takes place through their communication patterns, and healthy functioning is the extent to which the patterns of the family are effective and beneficial in achieving its goals. Family functioning is defined in seven dimensions, problem solving, communication, individual role, emotional companionship, emotional intercourse, behavior control and overall family functioning. Problem solving and optimal family functioning are concepts that have a direct impact on family needs, goals, life satisfaction and emotional relationships. Also, the individual role and the family function are interdependent, and a healthy family, according to Miuchin, is a family in which the roles of the members complement it.[19]

Because procrastination causes important objective (such as loss of time) and emotional consequences (such as weakening of morale, increased stress and anxiety, and low motivation) (Van Wyk, 2004; quoted by Sepehriyan, 2010). This behavior causes students to fail and as a result, the goals of education are not fulfilled. Considering that understanding the procrastinating behaviors effective on the learning process of students facilitates the use of their skills to effectively deal with procrastinating behavior (Kagan, 2010) and also conducting extensive research in this field, the causes related to this issue Comprehensive, remains in a veil of ambiguity, it seems necessary to conduct more research in relation to this psychological variable. A very important point is that, contrary to the very simple idea of procrastination, procrastination is a very complex phenomenon that even people, despite being aware of their procrastination and committing to not procrastinating, still engage in procrastination. They continue, because this behavior may be rooted in a person's way of thinking and other characteristics that are stable. Therefore, research on the factors and cases that lead to academic procrastination is of great importance.[19]

Academic failure has been observed as one of the problems of educational systems in all countries and it brings many spiritual, psychological, family and social consequences for students. If we consider academic failure as the actual failure of students to reach their potential. In this case, even among gifted students, academic failure is possible. So, it becomes necessary for the researcher to investigate the causes of this problem. Since the drop in education causes the loss of financial resources and creates bad mental and emotional effects on students and their families and makes them run away from school and drop out. Therefore, any research that can somehow deal with the nature of the causes and consequences of this issue will certainly be helpful. Academic failure also leads to emotional and social problems. Therefore, according to the said material, what is important is to investigate the factors of academic failure, procrastination and anxiety of students based on parenting styles. The meaning of academic failure is the reduction of a student's academic performance from a satisfactory level to an unfavorable level. Academic failure causes a lot of financial and human resources to be wasted, and improving the efficiency of

educational systems depends to a large extent on preventing wastage or reducing academic failure. To pave the way for the success of more students by knowing the possible factors that cause academic failure. In recent years, this issue has occupied the minds of those who care about the education system, and several solutions have been proposed to prevent this phenomenon.[20]

4. Conceptual and operational definition of variables:

4.1 Conceptual definitions

Parenting style: Parenting style is a system of attitudes about the child, the way to communicate with the child, the method of keeping the child, and the emotional atmosphere that governs the behavioral space of the parents. (Stenberg, 2002). Parenting methods refer to the methods that parents apply in dealing with their children, which can have a great and profound effect on the growth and development of a person during childhood and the subsequent characteristics of his personality (Masch and Barkley, 2012). [21]

Procrastination: Academic procrastination means postponing things and doing things that have a lower priority. Such as: procrastination in preparing and presenting assignments, not completing assignments and not doing them, and even not preparing for the exam.[21]

Academic failure: The word "failure" means falling, lack, and low caste, and academic failure means failure in education, dropping out of school or dropping out early, repeating the basic level of education, reducing grades, or failing in the education system.[21]

Anxiety: Anxiety is an unpleasant and often vague feeling of worry that is accompanied by one or more physical symptoms such as heart palpitations, shortness of breath, feeling empty, sweating, restlessness, and the urge to move. (Rosenhan and Seligman 2005; translated by Seyed Mohammadi, (2010).[22]

4.2 Operational definitions

Parenting style: In this research, to determine the parenting style, the researcher intends to use Diana Bamerind's Parenting Questionnaire (1973). The scale of this style has 3 components. which include: assertive style, authoritarian style, and permissive style. Determining the type of parenting in each type depends on the scores that each subject gets from the questionnaire.[23]

Procrastination: In this research, procrastination is the score that a student gets from the procrastination questionnaire of Solomon and Rothblum (1984). [24]

Academic failure: academic failure means the reduction of academic performance and lessons of students from a satisfactory level to an unfavorable level. Generally, it is the time when his grades show a noticeable downward trend compared to the previous month or previous years. So comparing and measuring the level of previous and current academic performance of students is the best indicator of academic failure. [25]

Anxiety: In this research, anxiety refers to the score that the student gets from the Phillips (1978) anxiety questionnaire. [25]

5. Theoretical foundations and research history of this research

The family is the most suitable system for providing the material, mental and spiritual needs of human beings and provides the best environment for providing the security and mental comfort of the members, raising the new generation, socializing the children and meeting the emotional needs (Rahim Aghaei, Shahbazi, 2014). On the other hand, the family is a result or a reflection of the whole

society. The main and obvious role of the family is to transfer cultural and religious values and heritage from breast to breast, maintain kinship relationships, raise and educate the generation and provide basic human needs and finally psychological and emotional interaction among its people (Nawabinejad, 2015).

And also, family interactions are one of the most basic aspects of the family and one of the main influencing factors in the growth process of family members, especially children, and it means the quantity and quality of communication between parents and children. A relationship that, taking into account a range of structural rules, determines the power, role, duties and rights of the parties and in a format combined with intimacy, existing communication continuity and continuity, makes this social system possible during the possible time (Habibi and Mazaheri and Dehghani, 2013). One of the main human needs is the need to interact and communicate with others, one of the most well-known interactions within the family. Interactions that, while creating a sense of security and peace in people, enable the formation of the family system and its continuity over time (Javidi et al., 2014).

Perhaps it can be said that the most important effective factor in the formation of a student in relation to education is the family. How parents deal with students and their lessons and what kind of behaviors they value in their educational models is one of the basic factors in the formation of students' attitudes towards education. If the family's attitude towards school, teachers and lessons is negative. Or if there is a difference between what they say and what they do, it is natural that gradually, their child will also have a negative attitude towards studying. Although many researches such as Afzali (2012), Nestin and Cecilia (2016) have confirmed the role of family interactions in academic failure, however, the nature of this relationship and how the family interactions of students with academic failure are exactly known is not [26].

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6. Methodology

Type of research method and expression of variables

The descriptive research method was correlation type. The statistical population included all sixth-grade female students of Arak district 2.

The predictor variable is parents' parenting styles, and the criterion variables are work procrastination, academic failure, and anxiety.

Information collection method

The method of collecting information is field and library. Also, the researcher has collected information by using standard questionnaires and checking students' scores [28].

The research community

The research population consisted of 2100 sixth grade female students of government and non-government primary schools in the 2nd district of Arak along with their parents in the academic year of 2020-2021.[29]

Sampling method and sample volume

The statistical population of this research was first prepared through the Department of Education, District 2, and the number of 2100 sixth grade female students of public and private schools in the academic year of 2019-2019 was determined, and then it was included in Morgan's table, and the number of 370 people made up the statistical sample. formed. In this research, cluster random sampling method was used. That is, in the first stage, out of districts 1 and 2, district 2 was randomly selected, and in the second stage, two government schools and two non-government schools were also randomly selected. And then in the third stage, 200 students from government schools and 170 students from non-government schools and a total of 370 people were randomly selected and entered into the study. Of these, about 70 people answered the questionnaires due to various reasons (problems encountered). They didn't and at the end 300 people answered the questionnaires and entered the study.[30]

Research tools

Information gathering tools (questionnaire, interview, observation, test, fiche, table, sampling, laboratory equipment and databases and computer and satellite networks, etc.)

Questionnaire of Diana Baumrind parenting form

This questionnaire, whose initial form was designed in 1973 by Diana Baumrind. It contains 30 items, 10 of which are permissive, 10 are authoritarian, and the other 10 are decisive and reassuring.

The questionnaire was translated by Hosseinpour (1973). The agent measures. Sentences No. 28, 24, 21, 19, 17, 14, 13, 10, 6, 1 in a lenient manner and sentences Nos. 29, 26, 25, 16, 12, 9, 7, 3, 2, 1 Authoritarian methods and sentences 30, 27, 23, 22, 20, 15, 11, 8, 5, 4 are related to a decisive and reassuring manner [32].

In this research, the purpose of determining the parenting styles of parents is the score that the parents of the students get in response to the 30-item questions of the parental parenting form questionnaire. Questionnaires, data are entered into the SPSS software. Of course, before entering the data, the questionnaire must be defined in the SPSS software and then start entering the data [32].

Questionnaire scoring

The pattern of answering the questions follows the 5-point Likert scale. In this way, the mother is asked to choose the answer that best matches the existing situation from among the 5 answers of completely agree, agree, not sure, completely disagree and disagree. In addition to the answering pattern, the scoring of Diana Bamrind's questionnaire questions is also based on a Likert scale, which is graded from 0 to 4. Three separate scores are obtained by adding the scores of the questions related to each method and dividing it by the number of questions.[33]

Validity and reliability of data collection tools

- Validity deals with how well a measurement instrument measures something.

- Reliability or reliability of an instrument is its degree of stability in measuring whatever it measures, that is, to what extent the measuring instrument gives the same results under the same conditions (Sarmed et al. 2013).[34]

Validity and reliability of this questionnaire have been confirmed. Borai (1991) used the differential method to check the validity and reliability of this questionnaire. And he observed that authoritarian style has a negative relationship with laxity and logical authority. And the way of complacency had no significant relationship with the way of his logical authority. (Mehrafrooz, 2018).[35]

In the Institute of Psychiatry of Iran, Esfandiari (1374), translated the original form of the questionnaire and made the necessary corrections in it, and has reported the validity of this test according to the opinion of experts and psychologists. which has high validity and reliability of this test based on the test-retest method, on a group of 12 mothers with a time interval of one week. which reported 69% in the permissive method, 77% for the authoritarian method and 73% for the democratic method. Tankabani (1379) also reported the reliability coefficient of the questionnaire as 72%. The content validity of the test was also confirmed by 10 experts in psychology and psychiatry (cited by Gotalizadeh 2019).[36]

Academic procrastination questionnaire

This questionnaire was created by Solomon Wrathblum in (1984) and it was called the academic procrastination scale. This scale was used by Dehghani (1387) for the first time in Iran. which has 27 items. The academic procrastination questionnaire included 3 components, which are: 1. preparing for exams (8 items), 2. preparing for assignments (11 items) and 3. preparing for end-of-semester exams (8 items). Solomon (1988), citing Dehghani, 2017) reported a coefficient of 84% for internal consistency.[37]

Questionnaire scoring

The questionnaire consists of a set of questions about academic issues that are formulated on a Likert scale. When answering the questionnaire, subjects rate their situation on a 4-point scale, from never, rarely, most of the time, and always. In this scale, items (2, 4, 11, 13, 15, 16, 21, 23, 25) are scored in reverse.[37]

Validity and reliability of data collection tools

This questionnaire was translated into Farsi by Jokar and Delavarpour (2016) in Iran, and its validity and reliability were 61% and 88%, respectively. Namian and Hosseinchari (2013) in research titled "Explanation of students' academic procrastination based on religious beliefs and core of control", the reliability coefficient using Cronbach's alpha method was 70%.[37]

Phillips School Anxiety Questionnaire

This questionnaire was made by Phillips in (1978). In order to measure students' anxiety level, he made and measured four factors. which are: 1. Fear of self-expression and self-expression 2. Exam anxiety 3. Uncertainty in facing the expectations of others and meeting them 4. Physiological reaction related to the low tolerance of a person against stress. This test was translated in Iran by Riahi and Akbari (1371) and they selected 65 questions out of 74 questions due to many cultural differences. Abul Maali et al. have reduced the number of questions to 52 items in research titled reliability, validation of the test anxiety scale.[38]

Questionnaire scoring

The scoring of this test is done in such a way that the subject answers them in the form of yes, no and sometimes. His total score is obtained from the sum of the scores of each question.[38]

Validity and reliability of data collection tools

According to the three evidences of face validity, simultaneous criterion and construct validity, Abul Maali et al confirmed the validity of this test. Also, the reliability of the questionnaire is calculated using SPSS software.

Variable name: school anxiety

Cronbach's alpha: 88/.

Assessment of academic failure

In order to measure the academic drop of students, they were identified and evaluated based on the grades they obtained at the end of each semester [39].

Research implementation method

In order to select the research sample, first of all, the General Directorate of Education and Education of the province was referred to, and while confirming the parenting questionnaires of Diana Bamrind (1973), the procrastination questionnaire of Solomon and Rothblum (1984) and the anxiety questionnaire of Phillips school (1978) and obtaining approval, from the districts 1 and 2 of the cities. Arak, district 2 was randomly selected. Also, the total number of 2100 sixth grade female students of government and non-government schools in the academic year of 1399-1400 was determined and then included in Morgan's table and the number of 370 students was determined as a statistical sample. Among the schools, two government schools and two non-government schools were randomly selected. Among the students of these schools, 370 people were randomly selected as a research sample, of which 200

people were studying in government schools and 170 people were studying in non-government schools. And during negotiations with school counselors and principals and getting approval from them, as well as checking the students' half-year grades, they were identified and the questionnaires were available through the Shad application (due to the spread of the corona disease and the unavailability of the research sample). Students and their parents were included. Then data was collected with the cooperation of students and their parents. Among the 370 people in the research sample, 70 people refused to fill the questionnaire for some reasons. And 300 people answered the questionnaires. In order to analyze the data, SPSS software version 23 was used and the data was

analyzed by Pearson correlation test and multiple linear regression analysis [40].

Information description and analysis method

The method of data analysis is a part of descriptive statistics that determines demographic characteristics such as the age and educational level of students, the level of education of parents. The other part is the inferential statistics that were used by the Pearson correlation test. And the multiple linear regression test determines whether it is possible to predict academic procrastination, academic failure and student anxiety through parenting styles. The researcher has used these methods [40].

Figure 1.

Based on Figure 1, it can be said that the number of errors in the research variables is normal to a large extent and there is no problem. As a result, the default assumption of normality of errors has also been observed. In the following,

we will examine the relationship between procrastination and permissive, autocratic and authoritarian parenting styles [40]

Figur 2.

Based on Figure 2, it can be said that the number of errors in the research variables is normal to a large extent and there is no problem. As a result, the default assumption of normality of errors

has also been respected. In the following, we will examine the relationship between academic failure and permissive, autocratic, and authoritarian parenting styles.[40]

Figure 3.

Based on Figure 3, it can be said that the number of errors in the research variables is normal to a large extent and there is no problem. As a result, the default assumption of normality of

errors has also been respected. In the following, the relationship between anxiety and permissive, autocratic and authoritative parenting styles will be investigated.[40]

7. Conclusion

The purpose of this research was to predict procrastination, academic failure and anxiety and parenting styles. The research sample included 300 students, whose parents answered the parenting styles questionnaire of Diana Baumrind (1972) and the students answered the academic procrastination questionnaire of Solomon Wrathblum (1984) and the Phillips school anxiety questionnaire (1978). In order to measure the academic drop of students, they were identified and evaluated based on the grades they get at the end of each semester. Also, the data were analyzed by Pearson correlation and multiple linear regression.

In this section, the explanation of the research hypotheses is mentioned, and according to the information obtained from the statistical surveys and theoretical discussions and research records contained in the second chapter, each of the hypotheses will be interpreted and concluded. After that, the limitations of the research are also stated and finally practical and research suggestions are given for the use of other researchers.

Examining the hypotheses

First hypothesis: based on parents' parenting styles, students' procrastination can be predicted.

According to the results obtained from the Pearson correlation analysis, there is a significant and direct relationship between procrastination and the components of authoritarian parenting style and permissive parenting style, and there is a significant and indirect relationship with the authoritarian component. Also, the results of regression analysis showed that the components of permissive and authoritarian parenting style significantly predict the amount of procrastination. So that in the negligent and authoritarian component, this relationship is direct.[41]

The result of this hypothesis with the research results of Manadi and Esmaili (2015), Bazdar, et al. (2013), Sultannejad, Saadipour, Asadzadeh (2014), Ruin Tan, Naser Panah and Ruiin Tan (2014), Sourinejad, Farhadi and Kurdnoqabi (2014), Azarbadkan et al. (2015), Fereshte Nik Siret and Meluk Khademi Ashkzari, Vazpour et al. (2013), Suleiman and Hassan (2019), Khalid, Zhang, Wang, Ghafari and Pan (2019), Wu and Yeo (2019) are consistent.[42]

In explaining the result of this hypothesis, it can be said that it is actually the warm center of the family that makes people and people, and these constructions are more in childhood. Parenting styles are a combination of parenting behaviors that occur in a wide range of situations and create a lasting parenting atmosphere

(Laura Burke, 2017).[43] For example, personality dimensions of extroversion, agreeableness, and low emotional stability are highly correlated with authoritarian style (Haver et al., 2010). Considering the characteristics of the parents and their demands and the response of the children, each family chooses special methods of education and parenting that have shown a relationship with the appearance and maintenance of certain behaviors and characteristics in the children (Bamrind, 1991). It can also be said that authoritarian parenting is characterized by high demands from parents and their low responsiveness. Authoritarian parents have very high expectations from their children, low self-esteem is one of the characteristics of the children of authoritarian families, and since low self-esteem is one of the factors causing procrastination, it can be said that one of the reasons for the procrastination of children of authoritarian families is their low self-esteem. Another reason for this could be that the children of authoritarian parents suffer from a kind of perfectionism, perfectionism causes procrastination (Bashart and Farahmand, 2017)[44], that is, a person avoids that work due to the fear of failure and when he has to do something They postpone it until the last minute, and authoritarian parents destroy the sense of responsibility in their children by being too strict, and these children avoid dealing with tasks and do not do them until the last moment. On the other hand, authoritative parenting is one of the successful parenting styles. This style includes child rearing, acceptance and close interaction, adaptive control methods and appropriate independence for children. It is natural that since authoritative parents both give freedom to their children and supervise them, they see less reason to procrastinate and postpone things. Therefore, it can be said that this parenting style can have an inverse relationship with children's procrastination.[45]

The second hypothesis: based on the parenting styles of the parents, it is possible to predict the academic failure of the students.[46]

According to the obtained results, there is a significant and direct relationship between academic failure and permissive and authoritarian components, and a significant and indirect relationship with the authoritarian component. Also, the results of the regression analysis showed that only the authoritative parenting style component significantly predicts the degree of academic failure. So, this relationship is indirect. In other words, as the amount of authoritative parenting style increases, the amount of academic failure decreases.[46]

The result of this hypothesis with the research results of Jafari Nasir Mahaleh (1399), Darstkar, Javadi, Sepah Mansour (1391), Esmaili and Farahbakhsh (1394), Nik Siret, Khademi Ashkazari and Hashemi (1395), Nodei, Esmaili (1394), Maria C. Fontes et al. (2019), Kaysa Onola et al. (2019) and Onola, Statin, and Nurmi (2019), concur.[46]

In explaining the result of this hypothesis, it can be said that parenting style is a general pattern of caring that provides a context for child-parent educational behaviors, but it does not refer to a specific set of parental educational actions. Parenting practices are preparing the child to be on the path he has to take and once he goes through the stages of life, there will be no turning back. Parenting practices are defined as an integrated set of parental attitudes, goals and categories of parental duties, and it is assumed to create an emotional atmosphere for parent-child

communication. As a result, parenting is the result of a bipolar process that includes strong interconnected relationships and the presence of parents and children. This education may affect the education of the children of these parents. So that parents, through their parenting styles, have very important and significant effects on their children's academic progress at different levels of education. Adolescents and young people need trust, support, and close relationships with their families, especially their parents, to succeed in public and higher education and in their lives. For this reason, some researchers have suggested that family support for teenagers is a strong support during their life, especially during school years. Children and adolescents who grew up in families with authoritarian parenting styles perform better in school than those who grew up in families with other types of parenting styles. Easy parenting style is characterized by the lack of parental control and responsiveness to the child's demands. Also, the parenting style combined with the acceptance and encouragement of parents, which leads to the development of independence in their children, increases the confidence in the ability of these children. Also, according to Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory, important people in life, such as parents, play an important role in the formation of adolescent perceptions of personal values and abilities. Also, the involvement of parents in the educational affairs of their children is related to their academic progress. When parents are involved as a reliable source and role model in the academic activities of students at home, students feel more competent and competent and show more competence in academic affairs.[47]

Third hypothesis: Based on parents' parenting styles, students' anxiety can be predicted.

According to the obtained results, there is a significant and direct relationship between anxiety with permissive and authoritarian components, and a significant and indirect relationship with the authoritarian component. Also, the results of the regression analysis showed that the components of authoritarian and authoritarian parenting style increase the level of anxiety. It predicts significantly.[48]

The result of this hypothesis with the results of Hosseinpour and Babapour (2015), Ismailpour and Jamil (2013), Yagoubi Rad (2014), Nasiri and Mohammadzadeh (2013), Shafipour et al. – Levy (2021), Gorostiaget, Alliri, Baloderka, and Lamarinhas (2019), Fontes, Garciaros, Gonzalez, and Sancerni (2019), Schutt, Mudd, and McLachlan (2019), Zhou, Nie, Ran, and Zhang (2017), Suisa and Weiss (2014), Zakari, Nikar Esfahani and Razmjooi (2013), Writman and Assef (2010) are consistent.[49]

In explaining the result of this hypothesis, it can be said that each family, according to the characteristics of the parents and their demands and the response of the children, chooses special methods of education and parenting that have shown a relationship with the emergence and maintenance of special behaviors and characteristics in the children (Bamrind, 1991). Since the personality of each person determines his behavior, the way of parent-child interaction and parenting style, which is the set of behaviors, methods and words of parents towards their children, is also a function of their personality model. In other

words, childhood is a very sensitive and important period in the development and formation of a person's personality, and its effects remain until the end of life. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to child education in this period. Also, Baumrind considered each of the dictatorial, permissive and democratic parenting methods to be effective in children's cognitive and social ability. In the permissive parenting method, parents ignore and accept the child's behavior, they do not use punishment as much as possible, and their expectations for the behavior developed in the child are small. In a dictatorial parenting style, parents feel they have to control everything, they have a set of rules that must be followed. Children have little freedom. Discipline is usually a form of reward and punishment. Children soon learn to please their parents in order to receive a reward. For this reason, they may perform behaviors out of fear of their parents, and rebel against their parents' control methods. Parents who are gentler and accepting in their interactions with their children pay more attention to their children. Of course, the relationship is mainly two-way. As the research of Sigoland, Kendall and Steinberg (1996) have also shown, children with anxiety disorders consider their parents more rejecting than healthy children. When these results are compared with parental control, the matter becomes clearer. More parental control and intervention takes away the independence of children's actions and this causes children's anxiety. The less controlling the parents are, the less anxiety the children will have. It has been clarified in the researches that the interaction patterns of mothers of children are anxious, annoying and controlling. Although Turner and colleagues (2003) did not find a difference between the parenting methods of anxious and non-anxious parents in their observational study, the strict parenting pattern in families with anxiety problems has been confirmed to a large extent, and as Hudson and Rapi (2001)) have also found that interventional education leads to the differentiation between mothers of healthy and anxious children.[50] Parents' anxiety and mother's rejection perception significantly predict children's anxiety. In other words, in addition to reducing parents' anxiety, mother's acceptance and attention or children's perception of mother's acceptance can be effective in reducing children's anxiety. The results of previous researches that have investigated the effect of treating parents' disorders on reducing children's problems are in a way supportive of this discussion. For example, the research of Farzadfar and Homan (2007) showed that teaching parenting skills to mothers is effective both in reducing stress on parents and in reducing children's behavioral problems. On the other hand, the research of Cobham et al. (1998) showed that in the presence of parental anxiety, the effectiveness of individual treatment interventions for children is less and the management of parental anxiety increases the effectiveness of treatment. According to the findings of this research and previous researches, it can be stated that mother and father's anxiety and controlling parenting methods of both parents and non-acceptance of children by both of them have very destructive psychological effects on children both in childhood and in He has youth [51-52]

Research proposals:

- Investigating such research on other related variables or other related factors with parenting styles and investigating the impact of society and culture on it.
- It is suggested that future researches should be conducted with a larger sample size and in a larger geographical area.
- This research should be done for male students as well as students of other grades.
- It is suggested that according to the theoretical foundations of the research, suitable moderating variables such as gender, socioeconomic class, parental literacy level, etc., should be included in the research and compared.

Practical suggestions:

- Announcing the results of such research to centers such as family therapy counseling centers in order to apply and pay more attention to parenting styles and differentiation in the direction of therapeutic interventions, as well as establishing educational sessions for educational coaches and parents in order to better understand the factors affecting academic failure and work procrastination, and students' anxiety and searching for its causes and origins in the family environment and educational environment is recommended.
- Holding classes on parenting styles and introducing and informing parents about the impact of their parenting styles and their children's academic success. Also, due to the simplicity of the concepts related to the components within the family, it is possible to conduct comprehensive and extensive training from written materials and educational videos and designing suitable computer sites.
- Considering the role of the family in the formation of procrastination in students, it is suggested that educational workshops be held for parents on the correct methods of raising children and the sensitive role of parents in the formation of students' personality. Also, during each semester, a training course on procrastination, the causes of procrastination and the problems caused by it will be held so that the students will get to know better and more about this phenomenon that causes lack of learning and hinders academic progress.

Also, by creating successful experiences, successful models, and verbal encouragements for students, parents and school staff can increase their self-confidence in order to reduce the level of academic failure, anxiety and stress of students. Also, parents and officials should pay more attention to the mental-psychological states of students, so that in case of signs of discomfort, they can be prevented from becoming chronic by taking quick action in this regard.

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